

Design Project for Shallow Foundation

Submit to:

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Abstract:

Foundation engineering is the application and practice of the Fundamental principles of soil mechanics and rock mechanics (i.e., Geotechnical engineering) in the design of foundations of various Structures. These foundations include those of columns and walls of buildings, Bridge abutments, embankments, and others. It also involves the Analysis and design of earth-retaining structures such as retaining walls, sheet-pile walls, and braced cuts.

Introduction:

Shallow Foundation.

Structural foundations grouped under two broad categories-

- shallow foundations.
- deep foundations.

A shallow foundation is one which is placed on a firm soil near the ground, and beneath the lowest part of the superstructure.

A deep foundation is one which is placed on a soil that is not firm, and which is considerably below the lowest part of the superstructure.

There is no exact definition which distinguishes one from the other.

Design Criteria for Shallow Foundation.

While considering a shallow foundation for a given loading system, the foundation must meet certain design requirements.

The three basic requirements are as follows:

1. Foundation placement, which involves the location and depth of foundation, requires a careful investigation of the past usage of the site and detailed information of the sub-surface stratum. The foundation placement should be such that any future influence should not affect its performance adversely.
2. Safety against bearing capacity is a requirement that involves suitable proportioning of the footing to avoid a catastrophic collapse of the soil beneath the foundation. This requirement makes it essential to have complete knowledge of the geo-technical properties of the soils and rocks involved. This occurs if the shear strength of the soil is inadequate to support the applied load.
3. Tolerable foundation settlement involves keeping a check on the excessive settlement of a structure. The excessive settlement is caused due to the distortion of the soil mass as a result of the applied shear stresses and due to the consolidation of the supporting soil. This again requires a complete knowledge of the geo-technical properties of the soil to assess the anticipated settlement of the structure and the time required for completion of the same.

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF SHALLOW FOUNDATION:

A foundation is defined as shallow when the depth of embedment (D_f) is less than the minimum lateral dimension of the foundation (B) (Figure 1). Shallow foundations have been widely used for ordinary buildings. An ideal foundation design should include all the information regarding to the soil and code practice. Soil parameters obtained from soil investigations obtained from site survey and laboratory studies should be used to construct an analysis model. The design should be based on the stability (overturning, bearing, etc.). In terms of cost, construction, material and labor work, shallow foundations have certain advantages over other types of foundations such as piles, piers, caissons and deep foundation. However, using shallow foundations when there is a problem of settlement, irregular ground surface or combined bending and axial loading might cause some problems.

The soil beneath the foundation has to carry the loads to be transferred from the superstructure upon it without any failure. Failure term here defines the case where there is an abrupt increase settlement under any additional load increment. Ultimate bearing capacity of the foundations (q_u) for framed structures is obtained by evaluating the limiting shear resistance of the soil

(Bowles, 1997). In ASD, the allowable bearing capacity, q_{all} , is then obtained by dividing q_u by a safety factor, F_s : between 2.5 to 3

The general bearing capacity for equations for soils was proposed by many researchers using bearing capacity parameters (Prandtl 1921, Reissner 1924,, Meyerhof 1951, Vesic 1963, Goodman 1989, etc.). Among the many ultimate bearing capacity equations, Terzaghi bearing capacity equation (Terzaghi, 1943) has been widely used in geotechnical engineering practice due to its ease on use. No shape, depth, etc. factors need to be determined.

Figure 1. A typical Shallow Foundation

Terzaghi's Bearing Capacity Theory

Terzaghi (1943) proposed a well-conceived theory to determine the ultimate bearing capacity of a shallow, rough, rigid, continuous (strip) foundation supported by a homogeneous soil layer extending to a great depth. The failure surface in soil at ultimate load assumed by Terzaghi (1943) is shown in Figure 2. Referring to Figure 2, the failure area in the soil under the foundation can be divided into three major zones:

1. Zone *abc*. This is a triangular elastic zone located immediately below the bottom of the foundation. The inclination of sides *ac* and *bc* of the wedge with the horizontal is $\alpha = \phi$ (soil internal friction angle).
2. Zone *bcf*. This zone is Prandtl's radial shear zone.
3. Zone *bfg*. This zone is the Rankine passive zone. The slip lines in this zone make angles of $\pm(45 - \phi/2)$ with the horizontal.

Terzaghi (1943) assumed that the soil located above the bottom of the foundation could be replaced by a surcharge load of $q = \gamma D_f$.

Figure 2. Failure surface in soil at ultimate load for a continuous rough rigid foundation as assumed by Terzaghi (Das 2009).

General bearing capacity equation:

$$q_u = C' N_C F_{cs} F_{cd} F_{ci} + q N_q F_{qs} F_{dq} F_{di} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_b N_\gamma F_{\gamma s} F_{\gamma d} F_{\gamma i}$$

ANALYTICAL STUDY:

Description of the Building

The column layout for part of a building that is to be constructed in Ottawa, ON is shown in Figure 1. Three boreholes are located within this part of the building and the SPT data, along with other subsurface information, are summarized in the borehole logs given in Figures 2a, b, c. You are required to design shallow foundations to support the dead and live loads from columns B2 or B4 using the limit states design approach. The loads on these columns are given in Figure 1. Ensure that both the ultimate limit state (bearing capacity) and the serviceability limit state (total and differential settlement) are not exceeded and use a minimum factor of safety of 3. The design criteria based on local codes are maximum total settlement = 25 mm, minimum depth of footing = 300 mm, and the finished grade elevation is 780 m. On the Wechat class group you will find an excerpt of the Canadian foundation engineering manual providing limiting values for total and differential settlement of foundations. You need to comply with CFEM guidelines in your design. Groundwater was not encountered in any borehole.

Hint: You need to develop a soil profile and select design soil parameters based on the information from the three borehole logs. Consider provided N-values as N60. The common practice is to design the footing under the largest column load and then use the maximum vertical stress under this footing to design the

other footings. Traditionally, this approach would ensure equal settlement of all

footings (i.e., no differential settlement). In your design, however, you should also consider that a footing with a lower load located on a weaker soil layer rather than the footing with the highest load may govern the design.

Figure 1: Column loads and borehole locations

We are working on Column B4 so here we are used borehole –BH1, BH2 for N_{60} value

												BORING LOG: BH-1							
												SHEET 1 of 1							
												PROJECT #:							
PROJECT:						CONTRACTOR:													
CLIENT:						DRILLER:													
CLIENT PROJECT:						INSPECTOR:													
COORDINATES N:				REF. ALIGNMENT:				RIG TYPE:											
E:				STATION:				DRILLING METHOD:											
LOCATION: Ottawa, ON						OFFSET:						HAMMER TYPE:							
COMMENTS:												SURFACE ELEV.: 781.5							
												TOTAL DEPTH: 23							
												START DATE:		TIME:					
												FINISH DATE:		TIME:					
Type/Symbol	Casing		Split Spoon	Ring Sampler	Shelby Tube	Cuttings	Cone Barrel	GROUNDWATER DATA											
	S	R	U	CU	C	Date	Time	Water Depth (m)	Casing Depth (m)	Hole Depth (m)	Symbol								
I.D.	34.93mm		63.50mm																
O.D.	50.80mm		76.20mm																
Length	457.20mm		457.20mm																
Hammer WT.	622.75 N			Drill Rod Size															
Hammer Fall	762mm			I.D. (O.D.)															
DEPTH BELOW SURFACE (m)	ELEVATION (m)	GRAPHIC	SOIL SAMPLE			BLOWS			N-VALUE	RECOVERY (m)	VISUAL MATERIAL CLASSIFICATION AND REMARKS	MOISTURE, %	DRY DENSITY	SAMPLES SENT TO LAB					
			TYPE	NUMBER	SYMBOL	DEPTH (m)	FROM	TO							0.10-4 mm	10-20 mm	30-45 mm		
780			S	51	X	0.5	0.957	4	9	9	14	.457							
5																			
775			S	52	X	6	6.457	20	21	17	36	.457							
10																			
770			S	53	X	10	10.457	12	14	10	24	.457							
15																			
765			S	54	X	14	14.457	25	30	41	71	.229							
20																			
760																			
25																			
EOB @ 23m. No ground water encountered.																			

Figure 2a: Borehole Log (BH-1)

										BORING LOG: BH-2					
										SHEET 1 of 1 PROJECT #:					
PROJECT: CLIENT: CLIENT PROJECT:										CONTRACTOR: DRILLER: INSPECTOR:					
COORDINATES N: E: LOCATION: Ottawa, ON					REF. ALIGNMENT: STATION: OFFSET:					RIG TYPE: DRILLING METHOD: HAMMER TYPE:					
COMMENTS:										SURFACE ELEV.: 781.5 TOTAL DEPTH: 20 START DATE: TIME: FINISH DATE: TIME:					
Type/Symbol	Casing		Split Spoon	Ring Sampler	Shelby Tube	Cuttings	Core Barrel	GROUNDWATER DATA							
	I.D.	O.D.	Length	Hammer WT.	Hammer Fall	Date	Time	Water Depth (m)	Casing Depth (m)	Hole Depth (m)	Symbol				
			S 34.93mm	R 63.50mm	U	CU	C								
			50.80mm	76.20mm											
			457.20mm	457.20mm											
			622.75 N	Drill Rod Size											
			762mm	I.D. (O.D.)											
DEPTH BELOW SURFACE (m)	ELEVATION (m)	GRAPHIC	SOIL SAMPLE		BLOWS			RECOVERY (m)	VISUAL MATERIAL CLASSIFICATION AND REMARKS	MOISTURE, %	DRY DENSITY	SAMPLES SENT TO LAB			
			TYPE	NUMBER SYMBOL	DEPTH (m) FROM TO	0-152.4 mm	152.4-304.8 mm						304.8-457.2 mm	N-VALUE	
7.80			S	S1	1	1.457	6	9	10	19	.457	Silty sand with gravel (SM)			
8.25			S	S2	2	2.457	11	12	10	22	.457	Poorly graded sand with trace of gravel (SP)			
7.75			S	S3	7	7.457	20	28	20	48	.457				
10			S	S4	9	9.457	10	13	15	28	.457	Lean clay, hard, dark brown to gray (CL)			
7.70			S	S5	14	14.457	25	35	31	66	.229	Well graded sand, very dense			
7.65															
20															
7.60															
25															
													EOB @ 20m. No ground water encountered.		

Figure 2b: Borehole Log (BH-2)

Step-1:

Calculating $(N_1)_{60}$, ϕ , Δ , C_N

Vertical stress: $\Delta' = \gamma'Z$

Correction Factor: $C_N = \sqrt{\frac{1}{(\Delta'/\rho_a)}}$

$(N_1)_{60} = C_N N_{60}$

γ' = Unit weight of soil (18 kN/M³)

ρ_a = atmospheric pressure (100kpa)

<i>BH1</i>				<i>BH2</i>				
$(N)_{60}$	$(N_1)_{60}$	σ_z	ϕ	$(N)_{60}$	$(N_1)_{60}$	σ_z	ϕ	C
14	33.04	18	45.71	19	36.48	27	47.01	
39	34.96	117	46.44	22	32.78	45	45.60	
24	17.52	188.1	38.72	48	41.28	135	48.73	
71	44.02	261	49.69	28	21.28	171	40.63	
				66	40.92	261	48.61	

From chart and via interpolation method:

$$(N_1)_{60} = 33.58 \approx 33$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Friction Angle: } (\phi_1)_{avg} &= \sqrt{20 \times (N_1)_{60}} + 20 \\ &= \sqrt{20 \times 33} + 20 \\ &= 45.41 \approx 45^\circ \end{aligned}$$

Step:-2: Load Calculation:

Here,

Dead load =100 KN

Live load =300 KN

Moment = 30 KN

Load In column- $1.2 \times 100 + 1.5 \times 300 = 570$

Self weight of footing =10% of column =57

Total load = $1.2 \times 100 + 1.5 \times 300 + 57.0 = 627 \text{ KN}$

Eccentricity, $e = M/Q = 30/627 = 0.048$

Choose the foundation as square Foundation as Square foundation

So, $B=L$

$$\begin{aligned}\therefore q &= \frac{G}{B^2} + \frac{6M}{B^3} \\ &= \frac{346}{B^2} + \frac{6 \times 30}{B^3}\end{aligned}$$

➤ General bearing capacity

$$q_u = C' N_C F_{cs} F_{cd} F_{ci} + q N_q F_{qs} F_{dq} F_{di} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_b N_\gamma F_{\gamma s} F_{\gamma d} F_{\gamma i}$$

$$\text{For } \phi' = 45^\circ, \quad c' = 0$$

$$N_q = 134.7, \quad N_\gamma = 271.3$$

Shape factor for square footing, $B/L = 1$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{so, } F_{qs} &= 1 + (B/L) \tan \phi' \\ &= 1 + 1 \times \tan 45^\circ \\ &= 1.85\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{And, } F_{\gamma s} &= 1 - 0.4 \times (B/L) \\ &= 0.6\end{aligned}$$

Assuming depth of Foundation $D_f = 3 \text{ m}$

$$\text{Depth factors } \frac{D_f}{B} \leq 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}F_{qd} &= 1 + 2 \tan \phi' (1 - \sin \phi')^2 \times \frac{D_f}{B} \\ &= 1 + 2 \tan 45^\circ (1 - \sin 45^\circ)^2 \times \frac{3}{B} \\ &= 1 + \frac{0.6}{B}\end{aligned}$$

$$F_{\gamma d} = 1$$

Inclination factors $F_{qi} = F_{\gamma i} = 1$

$$q = 18 \times 3 = 54 \text{ KN}$$

$$q_u = 54 \times 134.7 \times 1.85 \times \left(1 + \frac{0.6}{B}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \times 18 \times B \times 271.3 \times 0.6 \times 1$$

$$= 13456.53 + \frac{8074}{B} + 1465.02 B$$

[Here $F.S = 3$]

$$q_{all} = \frac{q_u}{FS}, \quad q_{all} = q$$

$$\frac{346}{B^2} + \frac{180}{B^3} = \frac{13456.53}{B} + \frac{8074}{3B} + \frac{1465.02B}{B}$$

$$\Rightarrow 14921.55B^4 - 8073.91B^3 - 1038B^2 - 540B = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow B = 0.71 \text{ m}$$

Step-3: Settlement

$$q_{max} = \frac{Q}{B^2} + \frac{6M}{B^3}$$

$$q_{min} = \frac{Q}{B^2} - \frac{6M}{B^3}$$

Here, $B = 0.7\text{m}$

$$q_{max} = \frac{627}{0.7^2} + \frac{6 \times 30}{0.7^3} = 1804.37$$

$$q_{min} = \frac{627}{0.7^2} - \frac{6 \times 30}{0.7^3} = 754.81$$

For $B \leq 1$

$$S_{C(mm)} = \frac{1.25 q_{net}}{N_{60} F_d}$$

$$q_{Average} = \frac{1804.37 + 754.81}{2}$$

$$= 1279.59 \text{ KN/M}^2$$

$$q_{net} = q_{avg} - \gamma D_f$$

$$= 1279.59 - 54 = 1225.59 \text{ KN/M}^2$$

Depth factor,

$$\begin{aligned} F_d &= 1 + 0.3 \left(\frac{D_f}{B} \right) \\ &= 1 + 0.3 \left(\frac{3}{0.7} \right) \\ &= 2.29 \end{aligned}$$

For, N_{60} by interpolation method

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N_{60} - 14}{9.7 - 0} &= \frac{19 - N_{60}}{10 - 9.7} \\ \Rightarrow 184.3 - 9.7N_{60} &= 0.3N_{60} + 4.2 \\ \Rightarrow 10N_{60} &= 1801 \\ \Rightarrow N_{60} &= 18.01 \end{aligned}$$

So, Settlement:

$$\begin{aligned} S_c &= \frac{1.25 \times 1225.59}{18.01 \times 2.29} \\ &= 37.1 \approx 37 \text{ mm} > 25 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

The settlement is greater than the maximum settlement, so we need to increase the footing

Let,

$$B = 1 \text{ m}$$

$$q_{max} = 807$$

$$q_{min} = 447$$

$$q_{avg} = 627, \quad q_{net} = 573$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned} S_c &= \frac{1.25 \times 573}{18.01 \times 2.29} \\ &= 17.36 \approx 17.5 < 25 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

so, $B = 1 \text{ m}$, than the settlement is ok.

